

A Study on Clean India Movement at Sivakasi

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Abstract

Adequate drinking water, sanitation, and hygiene, these are all the vital ingredients to make certain human health. Another essential and true factor is proper wastewater management and garbage disposal which is a basic prerequisite for health of environmental. Improving upon these services will bring economic gains which will help to build resilience there by giving increasing climate variability. The perception of the gender wise, particularly the women regarding the public health and hygiene are essential influencing factor in conditioning the practice of hygiene in all the community. The study motivates to keep the environment clean and hygiene, brochures can be issued to whole things. In brochures consist to related information, like, safe water, better sanitation, personal hygiene, disposal of waste etc. It is to be visited the rural area this information can be conveyed by this activity. In our people can be facing the door steps to explain about the brochures. And also this study to be created awareness to an illiterate people, but at the same way it's not at an easy task. In both community i.e., male and female will be get benefit from the awareness. Moreover, awareness camps and trainings are also focused to the students, which have the support of students will lead on great success. So the study focused towards the student's community too. In this study, giving the awareness videos like safe drinking water, better sanitation, Environmental cleaning, kitchen management, bio-degradable & non-biodegradable waste and pollution through the Educational communication, the students will be followed. Hence through this study steps has been taken to give power to the students (especially Sivakasi regional) towards the “Clean India Movement”.

Keywords: Wastewater management, Garbage Disposal, Students Community and Clean India

Introduction

In India, Earth's surface is roofed with 71% by water, 29% of it is land and 24.16 % of forest. Because of self-satisfaction, the waters are polluted and forest are smashed and emerged as buildings. Instead of looking green our country was filled with wastes. If the waste disposed of the apposite places, there is no need for any scheme any laws and any activity. The irresponsibleness of the people leads to investing a part amount for the cleaning process. These amounts are the people's tax money. If it is realized they didn't do it. Only the strict laws can make a change or the changes can be emerging from us.

As the entire nations encourage the cleanliness drives and campaigns under the impetus of ‘Swachh Bharat Abhiyan’ launched by the Honorable Prime Minister of India, Mr. Narendra Modi, let's

to be contributing and building ourselves clean India first. Amit Abraham has very wisely said “Clean your mind and our country will automatically get cleaned”. To ensure that, all should become the real participant in this crusade against the dirt or squalor in true spirit.

Cleanliness drive shall initiate from own home and surroundings. Zeal and enthusiasm for the cleanliness take are useless, if our own home and surroundings are unclean and spending more hours to cleaning the streets in other areas.

In the way of enhanced to start this cleanliness drive is own room, own cupboard, own toilet, own kitchen, own garbage. Remember, only a lit candle can light other unlit candles. Similarly, people who keep themselves clean and their surroundings clean, can help other people to complete cleanliness objectives. Let the cleanliness begin at your own home! If each one starts maintaining cleanliness at his / her home, the whole nation will automatically become clean.

Another step, after continue the clean India and to preserve the greenery. The main consist of conserving and preserving the environmental health and cleanliness of the surrounding area. The task is reasonably Herculean. The only solution to the critical environmental issues is people’s mass participation in saving the environment. The massive forestation drive and stopping the use of fossil fuels altogether can resolve this problem.

Clean India and Green India are chief factor of one coin, i.e., sustainable development in India. In Clean India or Swatch Bharat Aviyan (SBA) was the vision of the father of the nation. Mahatma Gandhi was mindful of the poor situation of Indian rural people at that time and the dream of a cleaner India, where Mahatma Gandhi emphasized on cleanliness and hygiene as an intact function of surviving.

The mission of Green India is a National Mission under the eight missions of the National Action Plan on Climate Change (NAPCC), recognizes that climate change phenomena will critically affect and alter the distribution, type and excellence of natural biological resources of the country and the associated livelihoods of the people. In India very close to the model of sustainable development. Hence, this paper is an attempt to enlarge the Green and Clean India as a model of Sustainable Development.

The Census taken on 2011, after that the census in our country clearly shows that 4,041 statutory towns (administrative units that have been defined by ‘statute’ as urban such as municipal corporations, municipalities, cantonment boards, notified town area committees, town panchayats or nagar palikas) and eight million households do not have access to toilets and defecate in the open. The weak sanitation has significant health regards and untreated sewage from statutory towns is the biggest source of water pollution in Indian context. It is to be indicating that, both the gauge of the challenge ahead of the Indian towns and the huge costs incurred from not addressing them.

It is necessary to keep our surroundings in clean because people get the fresh air, reduce pollution etc. An unclean surroundings leads to a bad condition of a society, arrival of diseases and many more.

With the ever rising use of technology and industries boom the amount of pollution in our environment is increasing at a rapid pace. Water pollution and litter are considered to be two of the main cause of the surroundings being dirty.

Whether the garbage is not cleaned, further it smells stench and welcomes the diseases and then people are affected through the bad garbage. Thus, if don’t keep our environment clean there would be many consequences or problems which will be faced by the society and people that live in that environment.

The world’s governments have pledged to make a better future where no one is left behind, yet the most basic conditions for people to survive and thrive are out of reach for many. Moreover per cent of our people inhale dirty air and those who die as a result are in low- and middle-income

countries, with women and young children disproportionately affected.

It is a nasty irony that the wealthiest in society -- who benefit most from the activities that pollute our environment – have the majority options to avoid the impacts. The poorest – who rely most on our surroundings for food, water, shelter and income – have the least access to safe alternatives. This creates a destructive cycle of poor health, poverty, inequality and migration that is hard to break.

In Government of India spends more than \$5 trillion a year on healthcare because of air pollution only. Also investing that in the kind of technologically and commercially viable solutions previously available would slow, perhaps even reverse, our ever-decreasing cycles of poverty and vulnerability. In doing so, we would not only improve health and create decent jobs; we would create more steady communities and more sustainable economic growth. A clean environment is not a luxury. It must be a right, and it is a massive opportunity for sustainable social and economic development.

Statement of the Problem

People most of the times throw litter and dust on the footpaths and roads instead of throwing it in dustbins. It is how slowly the litter accumulates and transforms into huge garbage. If this garbage is not cleaned, further it smells stink and welcomes the diseases and then people are affected by it. People show their status and financial strengths in their own luxury vehicles. If an individual has its own vehicles it also creates air pollution. In this connection, the environment gets affected. Hence it tempts to study the impact of clean India movement in Sivakasi.

The Scope of the Research

In the place of environment, where human being as well as plants and animals live. In that environments are kept it clean and neat, that is our major responsibility. An unclean environment leads to a bad condition of a society, arrival of diseases and many more things are happened. So, all the people should keep the environment clean and green for all the way of living. Its implementing on it everybody can reduce pollution; get fresh air, live a peaceful life without any problems.

Objectives of the Study

1. To study the impact of cleanliness that creates land pollution and soil contamination.
2. To generate public awareness about the drawback of open defecation and promotion of latrine use.
3. To ensure solid and liquid waste management through gram panchayats.

Research Design

1. The sampling frame includes that in which period the activities take place. The study carried out of 102 hours.
2. The sampling method for our research is that convenience sampling.
3. The sampling unit of the population was the illiterate people in residence, because they didn't become of the environment and its problem.
4. The sampling size was the population of 85 houses on the particular area.
5. The photos collected by the team were considered as the primary data.
6. Secondary sources used are some review of literature available in the websites.
7. Wall painting on public buildings is the activity that takes place in that area. The painted number is one and its size is 4×4 . The estimated number of people sensitized is one hundred and fifty, and the number of hours spent is six.

8. A door-to-door meeting is another activity which can be conducted at the place of Rajiv Gandhi Nagar. The number of households visit is sixty. A number of people sensitized is one hundred and fifty and number of hours spent is thirty-five.
9. Awareness Campaigns were conducted at Arasan Ganesan Matriculation Higher Secondary School Sivakasi. Number of awareness drives conducted was two. The number of people sensitized was hundred and ten and a number of hours spent were sixteen.
10. Issuing notice activity was taking place on the road sides of the specified area. The notice was pasted on the walls also. The number of beneficiaries were one hundred and fifty and number of hours spent was ten.
11. Street cleaning was done at the streets of Rajiv Gandhi Nagar at 56 colonies in Narnapuram panchayat, Sivakasi. The Length of streets cleaned is 120 sq feet, Number of community participants is five and Number of hours spent is thirty-five.

Limitations of the Research

1. The study concentrates mostly on the street cleaning activity because of their own interest.
2. The area was limited to the west side of the particular area because of the convenience of the study and for our team.
3. The scheduled time of 100 hours was not utilized in all the activities; it takes more time to complete the action.

Findings

1. The study shows that the people in that area were relatively low perception and low practice about the disposal of solid waste.
2. There were over-extraction of soil, water, land, and its resources etc.
3. Sources of water can be exploited and it was converted into buildings and industries.
4. Emission of toxic gases by the industries.
5. People do not have any awareness about the environmental problem, which was caused by their activities because they were illiterate.
6. The Scarcity of water arises due to Karuvelam trees.

Suggestions

1. The government should ensure solid and liquid waste management through gram panchayats and adopting modern techniques in Management of E-Waste by providing dustbins in different localities. It also ensures plastic and harmful materials withdrawn permanently.
2. The government must act strictly to ban on fossil fuels. Toxic emissions of industries must be strictly regularized.
3. The government must create forest belt near every city or town. Trees will help in controlling the pollution at least a little bit. So having lots of trees in the society will help to have fresh air and maintain good health.
4. Deforestation of karuvelam trees leads to reduce the water scarcity and heat of the environment.
5. Government and NGO's should try to provide the sources of waters like water tanks, ponds etc.

Conclusion

Clean India Movement can be attained by construction of individual sanitary latrines for households below the poverty line with subsidy (80 percent) where demand exists; conversion of

dry latrines into low-cost sanitary latrines; construction of exclusive village sanitary complexes for women providing facilities for hand pumping, bathing, sanitation and washing on a selective basis where there is not adequate land or space within houses and where village panchayats are willing to maintain the facilities; setting up of sanitary marts; total sanitation of villages through the construction of drains, soakage pits, solid and liquid waste disposal, and, Intensive campaign for awareness generation and health education to create a felt need for personal, household and environmental sanitation facilities.

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